

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride by Chloramine-B in Hydrochloric Acid Medium

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The kinetics of oxidation of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (HH) by chloramine-B (CAB) in hydrochloric acid medium have been studied at 0°. The reaction shows a first order dependence in [CAB], first order in [HH] and is independent of [H⁺]. The reaction is catalysed by Cl⁻ and the order in [Cl⁻] is unity. Addition of the reaction product benzene sulphonamide and increase in ionic strength of the medium have negligible influence on the rate of reaction. The effect of changing the dielectric constant of the medium on the reaction rate has been studied. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. Plausible mechanism has been proposed for the observed kinetics.

KINETICS of oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols¹, dimethyl sulphoxide², unsaturated alcohols^{3,4}, 2-methylphenol⁵ and aniline⁶ by chloramine-B (CAB) have been reported. In continuation of our work on organic chloramines, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (HH) by chloramine-B in presence of hydrochloric acid. The results show some interesting features which are different from those observed in chloramine-T (CAT) and bromamine-T (BAT) reactions^{7,8}.

Experimental

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (S. Merck) was purified by recrystallisation. Its aqueous solution was prepared and standardised by bromatometry. Chloramine-B was prepared by literature method and its aqueous solution was standardised by the iodometric method⁹. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Kinetic measurements: To a solution containing the requisite amount of substrate, acid, sodium perchlorate (to keep the ionic strength constant) and water (to keep the total volume constant throughout) was equilibrated at 0°, was added rapidly a measured quantity of CAB solution, pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was followed by iodometric estimation of the unconsumed CAB present in a measured aliquot of the reaction mixture withdrawn at regular intervals of time.

The stoichiometry of the reaction under the present conditions indicated that 1 mol of substrate consumed 3 mol of CAB according to equation (1),

where, R is C₆H₅SO₂. The reaction product, benzene sulphonamide was detected by tlc using petroleum ether-chloroform-n-butanol (1:1:0.5, v/v) as the solvent system with iodine as the developing reagent. The nitrate ion in solution was detected as usual.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of HH by CAB were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants. At constant [HCl] with [HH] in excess, the plots of log [CAB]₀ against time are found to be linear indicating a first order dependence in [CAB]₀. The pseudo-first order rate constants in CAB at different initial concentrations are given in Table 1

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS ON RATE OF REACTION AT 0°

[H⁺]=0.20 mol dm⁻³, [Cl⁻]=0.20 mol dm⁻³, μ=0.5 mol dm⁻³

[CAB] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[HH] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
3.0	5.0	6.96
4.0	5.0	6.91
5.0	5.0	6.95
6.0	5.0	6.90
7.0	5.0	6.98
5.0	2.5	4.01
5.0	7.5	7.68
5.0	10.0	13.73
5.0	12.5	17.91
5.0 ^a	5.0	6.85
5.0 ^b	5.0	6.84
5.0 ^c	5.0	6.94

^aIn presence of excess benzene sulphonamide. ^bIn total strength of 1.0 mol dm⁻³. ^cIn absence of [H⁺].

The rate is first order in [HH] as evident from the plots of log k against log [HH]. The rate of reaction increases with the increase in [HCl] (0.05-

0.40 mol dm⁻³). The plot of log *k* against log [HCl] is linear with unit slope confirming first order dependence in [HCl]. Addition of chloride ion increases the rate of reaction. Keeping [H⁺] (0.2 mol dm⁻³) constant, [Cl⁻] in solution was varied (0.22–0.35 mol dm⁻³) by adding sodium chloride. The plot of log *k* against log [Cl⁻] gives a straight line with unit slope. Since chloride ion was found to catalyse the reaction, [Cl⁻] in solution was kept constant (0.3 mol dm⁻³) and [H⁺] was varied (0.1–0.25 mol dm⁻³). It was found that the rate is independent of [H⁺]. To confirm this, [H⁺] in solution was neutralised and the rate constant was determined which agrees with that of the standard run (Table 1). Addition of the reaction product, benzene sulphonamide to the reaction mixture had no effect on the rate. Increase in the ionic strength of the medium from 0.5 to 1.0 mol dm⁻³ had negligible effect (Table 1).

The dielectric constant of the medium was varied by adding ethanol to the reaction mixture. The rate of the reaction increased, and plots of log *k* vs 1/*D* (where *D* is dielectric constant of the medium) gave a curve with a positive slope. The results are shown in Table 2. The reaction was studied at various temperatures. The energy of activation (*E_a*) was found to be 73.5 kJ mol⁻¹. Table 3 gives the results of activation parameters.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT ON RATE OF REACTION AT 0°

[CAB]=5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [NH₂OH.HCl]=5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, [Cl⁻]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, μ=0.5 mol dm⁻³

EtOH %	<i>D</i>	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	4 + log <i>k</i>	1/ <i>D</i>
0	87.0	6.95	0.842 1	0.011 49
10	81.0	16.27	1.211 5	0.012 34
20	74.0	21.49	1.322 3	0.013 51
30	67.9	24.05	1.381 2	0.014 71
40	61.5	26.26	1.419 3	0.016 26

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF TEMPERATURE ON RATE OF REACTION

[CAB]=5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [NH₂OH.HCl]=5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, [Cl⁻]=0.2 mol dm⁻³, μ=0.5 mol dm⁻³

<i>T</i> K	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	Δ <i>S</i> [‡] e.u.	Δ <i>H</i> [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹	Δ <i>G</i> [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹
273	6.95	-10.39	17.03	19.87
276.5	10.02	-10.51	17.02	19.98
278.5	17.21	-9.91	17.02	19.78
280.6	19.19	-10.18	17.01	19.87
282.5	21.43	-10.39	17.01	19.94
284.2	23.34	-10.61	17.01	20.02

Average values: Δ*S*[‡] = -43.24 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, Δ*H*[‡] = 71.23 kJ mol⁻¹, Δ*G*[‡] = 83.30 kJ mol⁻¹.

The possible oxidising species in acidified solution of CAB are RNHCl, RNCl₂ and HOCl. If RNCl₂ were to be the reactive oxidising species, the rate law predicts a second order dependence of rate on [CAB] which is contrary to the experimental

observations. If HOCl were to be the active species, a first order retardation of the rate by the added benzene sulphonamide would be expected, but no such effect has been noticed.

The following Scheme accounts for the experimental results,

Scheme 1

Then the rate law is

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{CAB}] [\text{HH}] \quad (2)$$

The effect of variation of [Cl⁻] on the oxidation kinetics of HH can be accounted for by the mechanism,

Applying steady state conditions, the rate law is

$$\text{Rate} = Kk_3 [\text{CAB}] [\text{HH}] [\text{Cl}^-] \quad (3)$$

In the case of oxidation of hydroxylamine hydrochloride by CAT^v in HCl medium, Katgeri *et al.* observed that the reaction is first order in [CAT] and [HH] and inverse first order in [H⁺]; and with BAT^s, the same authors noticed that the reaction is first order each in [BAT] and [HH] at low [HH], and zero order in [HH] at high [HH]. First order rate was observed in [H⁺]. But with CAB, the rate is found to be first order in [CAB] and [HH]. The rate is found to be independent of [H⁺] while it is first order in [Cl⁻]. In CAB oxidation the free acid RNHCl is assumed to react with HH in a slow and rate determining step.

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